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A simple approach for radargram pattern recognition: identification of metal and non metal object

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Ground Penetrating radar is an active geophysical methods which is mostly used to interpret objects buried under the surface or to determine the distribution of shallow subsurface sediments. Radargram as one of digital recording signals forms on GPR is often analysed using variety of mathematics and physics attributes to determine subsurface objects. The recorded signal is the reflection of the electromagnetic wave with a specific parameter that depends on the antenna frequency. Metals such as steel (Fe_3C), iron (Fe_2O_3) and aluminium (Al_2O_3) can be visibly distinguished from non-metal on the surface, but when the object lies below the surface, it is very difficult to perform identification for each object, this research is done to see changes in patterns on radargram, by performing mathematics and physics approaches to identify changes of frequency, amplitude, velocity and density of the recorded signal wiggle, this study uses survey data with objects containing metal buried deep as 1-2 m and non-metal objects (sedimentary rock) that are in the same relative depth. Each wiggle processed by time-shifting (MST), de-wow, Gain, Filtering, background removal until the object become clearer than before (until the best resolution obtained). Visual interpretation of peak-trough which formed on the wiggle function of distance and depth can help accelerating the identification process so that the distinguish process between metal and non-metal can be easily performed. The results appear on the hyperbole pattern radargram for metal objects but not for non-metal objects.

Keywords: GPR, pattern recognition, radargram, wiggle.

A Simple Approach for Radargram Pattern Recognition: Identification of Metal and Non Metal Object

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Abstract

Ground Penetrating radar is an active geophysical methods which is mostly used to interpret objects buried under the surface or to determine the distribution of shallow subsurface sediments. Radargram as one of digital recording signals forms on GPR is often analysed using variety of mathematics and physics attributes to determine subsurface objects. The recorded signal is the reflection of the electromagnetic wave with a specific parameter that depends on the antenna frequency. Metals such as steel (Fe_3C), iron (Fe_2O_3) and aluminium (Al_2O_3) can be visibly distinguished from non-metal on the surface, but when the object lies below the surface, it is very difficult to perform identification for each object, this research is done to see changes in patterns on radargram (Pattern Recognition), by performing mathematics and physics approaches to identify changes of frequency, amplitude, velocity and density of the recorded signal wiggle, this study uses survey data with objects containing metal buried deep as 1-2 m and non-metal objects (sedimentary rock) that are in the same relative depth. Each wiggle processed by time-shifting (MST), de-wow, Gain, Filtering, background removal until the object become clearer than before (until the best resolution obtained). Visual interpretation of peak-trough which formed on the wiggle function of distance and depth can help accelerating the identification process so that the distinguish process between metal and non-metal can be easily performed. The results appear on the hyperbole pattern radargram for metal objects but not for non-metal objects

Key words: Radargram, GPR, Pattern Recognition, Wiggle.

1. Introduction

The use of electromagnetic fields for remote sensing is commonly used, in several cases its use for disaster mitigation, such as impact of forest fire disaster, flood and every of it use satellite technology, like SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) until optical images for some condition radar technology with utilization of electromagnetic wave, can be used for identification for subsurface condition or known as ground penetrating radar.

Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) is geophysical method that often used to identify of shallow object by using electromagnetic wave (EMW) in certain frequency. GPR concepts on magnetic wave is very similar with acoustic wave in seismic by transmitted signal into subsurface around field-target and received reflected-signal from the receiver sensors. Recordings of this data are called *radargram*.

GPR research generally utilizes electromagnetic wave by analyzing the difference in reflection velocity of recorded signal. this difference is result of impact of subsurface dielectric permittivity. This dielectric constant indirectly shows the characteristics of the subsurface. The time obtained when transmitting

and receiving signals is called the TWTT velocity (Two Way Time Travel) (Neal, 2004; Jol and Smith, 1991). This velocity provides an indication of boundary layer and object in subsurface area, thus the velocity of EM wave defined as function of velocity of electromagnetic wave in a vacuum divided by dielectric permittivity square root (Olhoeft, 1998).

The purpose of this study is to characterize an object under the surface by using pattern recognition, objects that have been identified will be recognizable to have elements of metal and non-metal based on the nature of electromagnetic wave response on the recorded wiggle the pattern recognition form and characteristics of this radargram will give contribution for accurate result and close to real condition. In this research do an approach with differentiation of velocity function from electromagnetic wave to show dielectric permittivity. constants and references are expected to be obtained to underlie the identification of metal and non-metal object. The result of characterization of this pattern recognition will then be able to show value with a certain standard for an object containing metal, the value is expected write in mathematical equation.

Research on GPR developed since the 19 century. (Reynolds 1997), and gives the definition that the electromagnetic field of an object will be linear with the content of the material and water components in the object, both of which also effect the propagation of electromagnetic waves, the magnitude of the reflected energy is determined by the contrast of the velocity of electromagnetic wave propagation and also by the dielectric constant of any material exposed to the electromagnetic field.

objects with certain physical parameters which are identified by GPR, on average have specific wave reflection responses, this specific response is still manually interpreted today by data processors and relies only on the expertise and experience of data processing operators. This becomes very uncertain and inaccurate if the data processors were inexperienced, therefore a mathematical approach is made to minimize misidentification by inexperienced data processors.

To assist in providing data and information which are needed to made formulation with mathematical approach, conducted field data retrieval, data taken at construction site in area of Tangerang, Banten province. Data was taken using 80 MHz antenna with 512 sampling rate and 256 time windows. Estimated velocity default velocity when measuring using 10 cm / ns. With a distance of 5-10 meters depending on the condition of the field.

2. Method

2.1 Concept.

The GPR system transmits a short pulse at high frequencies between 10 MHz-1000MHz from the antenna to the subsurface (Jol and Smith, 1991) GPR is always related to the Maxwell equations ie with electrical and magnetic components, this relationship is explained simply by Figure 2.1

Figure 2.1 simple schema of electric field and magnetic field which work on electromagnetic wave (David J. 2004).

Because electromagnetic waves are spread out below the surface, and their velocity will change due to exposure to materials that have certain

physical parameter values, so Maxwell's basic equations can be simplified to be.

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \vec{E} + \mu\sigma \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} + \mu\epsilon \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} = 0 \dots \dots (1)$$

where ∇ del Vector operator, $\vec{E}$ electric field vector, μ magnetic permeability, σ electric conductivity, ϵ dielectric permittivity, and ∂t differential function of time. (Harry M. Jol, 2008). The further investigation showing if propagation of electromagnetic wave is very influenced by dielectric of material If it is assumed that the medium is homogeneous then a definition of propagation EM waves can be write:

$$\gamma = \alpha + j\beta = \sqrt{(\sigma + j\omega\epsilon)j\omega\mu} \dots \dots (2)$$

With attenuation coefficient:

$$\alpha = \omega\sqrt{\mu\epsilon} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\omega\epsilon} \right)^2} - 1 \right] \right)^{1/2} \dots (3)$$

Phase coefficient:

$$\beta = \omega\sqrt{\mu\epsilon} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\omega\epsilon} \right)^2} + 1 \right] \right)^{1/2} \dots (4)$$

Wave Velocity (m/s)

$$v = \frac{c}{\left(\frac{\mu\epsilon}{2} \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\omega\epsilon} \right)^2} + 1 \right] \right)^{1/2}} \dots \dots (5)$$

With c = velocity wave on vacuum (3×10^8 m/s), ω = angular frequency, ϵ =absolute permittivity, ϵ =relative permittivity, μ =absolute permeability, μ =relative permeability, σ =conductivity (Harry M. Jol, 2008).

The equation can be simplified if the material's conductivity and the angular frequency are the part of the dielectric constant so that it can be rewritten to be:

$$v = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} \dots \dots (6)$$

Which is Electromagnetic velocity wave (v), equal with velocity of light in vacuum (c) divided with square root of dielectric permittivity (ϵ_r).

2.3 Survey Design and Data Processing

The survey focuses on field data containing the estimated metal elements in the form of building structures and also non-metallic elements. Survey technique using common offset profiling

Gambat 2.3 reflection scheme from EM instrument

The location of the survey was conducted in "Wista" construction area in Tangerang Selatan city, Banten Province.

Figure 2.4 field acquisition location

Data acquisition using instrument ground penetrating radar with center frequency of 80 Mhz, every data retrieval is done with distance of track average 6 meter or adjust condition of field. Data collection is done by geological identification as sedimentary rock area (Quarter). The data are processed by the scheme of processing. As in Figure 2.4

Gambar 2.5 flowchart data processing

Editing and processing of data are performed by the same process, but with varying values, this value arises from the heterogeneity of the measured medium. The filter application process in the data is (K.J. Sandmeier, 1998):

- de-wow, to reduce effects on recorded data due to low frequency or highpass filter,
- Time-zero Correction (Move Start Time) Is the correction of the initial time the EM wave arrives with the surface position

- Amplitude Gain Control is the process by which low amplitude is calculated by the high value of high amplitude,
- Bandpassfilter- Correction at high frequency and low frequency.
- Background removal - This filter results in an output value of the average trace (range) made based on the range of time / distance that appears on the radargram.
- De-convolution Is done using the Levinson algorithm to remove the EM spectrum of spike signals, and make it smoother without losing its real value
- Fk-filter is a Fourier transform to the range of data which will then be incorporated into the frequency domain of the wave number

Mathematical Process

If the function for velocity is defined by:

$$v = \omega A \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x - \frac{2\pi vt}{\lambda}\right) \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

So the equation can be defined:

$$v = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} = \omega A \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x - \frac{2\pi vt}{\lambda}\right) \dots \dots (8)$$

With:

ω = angular frequency, and λ = wave length.

The dielectric constant of the material actually becomes the focus of the calculation but to determine it required other physical parameters whose data are not obtained in this study.

3. Result and Discussion

Each data acquisition process requires direct surface identification (see Figure 2.6).

Figure 3.1 Instrument position of the data acquisition path and the surface conditions at which the data is collected

The results of the radargram will indicate the presence of metal objects in several locations, marked by high reflectance signals recorded on the radargram and different patterns of surrounding environments, as shown in Figure 2.7. Anomalies that are different from those of the surrounding environment obviously have their own mathematical value which will be defined in the formulation of the dielectric constant of the material, together with the possibility of the metal content it possesses.

Figure 3.2 identifies the presence of metal from the readings on the radargram

The data displayed on the processed radargram indicates the hyperbolic effects of an object or anomalous metal present beneath the surface. As shown in Figure 2.8

Figure 3.3. the A path indicating a metal indication visually looks like a strong reflectant.

Figure 3.4. the B path which also shows the metal indication visually.

Figure 3.5. the C path indicating a metal indication

Basically interpretation on radargram to identify the existence of metal content on the object only based on visual, but by doing mathematical formulation to approaching the value of visual reading variables, the formulas are expected to assist the operator in performing data analysis.

Figure 3.5 the path D indicating a metal indication

To be able to assist in the process of mathematical analysis carried out several approaches by first observing the recorded wiggle

Figure 3.6 Wiggle analysis for indicated data contains metal elements

From the wiggle data can be seen the parameter values of anomalies such as position, speed, TWT (Two-way Time), filtered Amplitude, angle, frequency and other wave parameters. These parameters will produce the value as the following trend

Mathematical result

Frequency depends on wave propagation speed, for experiments conducted using 80 MHz frequency.

Table 3.1 Anova and coefficient table from data (see Figure 3.8)

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	
1	Regression	19,751	2	9,876	12,302
	Residual	72,249	90	,803	
	Total	92,000	92		

Coefficients ^a				
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	Std. Beta
1	(Constant)	-4,026E-18	,003	
	Zscore(Amplitude)	-.072	,095	-.072
	Zscore(Speed)	-.473	,096	-.473

Based on the data conducted in the experiment, we get the following wave velocity model:

$$\hat{v} = -9,33 \times 10^{-18} - 0,72x_1 - 0,473x_2 \quad (9)$$

With:

$$x_1 = \omega A = 2\pi f \dots (10)$$

And

$$x_2 = \cos(\omega t - kx) \dots (11)$$

Where:

$\hat{v}$: States the wave velocity model (m/s)

ω : Express angular velocity (rad/s)

A: amplitude (m)

f :wave frequency (Hz)

t : time arrival of wave (s)

k : number of wave

x: wave distance (m)

Figure 3.7. Velocity model regression (normalize)

From the regression modeling for the value of velocity has been show that the data (see figure 3.8) value deviation is not too far away. This indicates that if the data collected have the same impulse response to the electromagnetic waves that hit the subsurface object.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	19,751	2	9,876	12,302	,000 ^a
	Residual	72,249	90	,803		
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Figure 3.8. Data input for mathematical model

The distribution data of velocity obtained from the data processing, still shows that the value

is still far relevance, because the data are far apart (see Figure 3.9), this can be effected by the process of propagation of electromagnetic waves on heterogenic medium still have noise or the sample values are less appropriate statistical rules

Figure 3.9 Scatter plot for dependent variable (velocity)

4. Conclusion

GPR is one method that utilizes EM waves to see shallow subsurface conditions with relatively high frequencies. In the use observers can quickly recognize the existence of subsurface anomaly due to the reflection caught on the receiver and recorded by the radargram, in recognition of anomaly conditions that contain metal observe depends only on most visual modes, approaches with equations to mathematical models is needed as an innovation in the development of data processing and minimize the existence of human error in data interpretation.

Based on observations with characteristic pattern recognition, it is known that the metal containing Fe (Iron & steel) has a parabolic reflection pattern with the mathematical approximation value of function as in equation (9), determination of dielectric constant as in the initial plan due to absence volumetric physical parameter data from the measurement

location. this research will be more accurate if used more data, and expected can become more applicable in assisting the interpretation process in next research study.

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Appendix

Typical GPR Data Processing flow: 2D bistatic Radar Reflection Profiling

